

Impulses, Schrodinger Equation and Newtonian Gravity

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 16, 2021

In a previous note (1), we argued that one may consider a potential $V(x)$ as being an average of impulse hits i.e. $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k,x)$ with the rule that $-d/dx V(k,x) = k V(k,x)$ i.e. k is the amount of momentum imparted to a quantum particle and $V(k,x)$ is a conditional probability $P(k/x)$. Thus, one works entirely with momentum at the level of impulse, so $p=m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ are treated in the same manner. One develops a formalism based on momentum and invariance i.e. $V(k,x)=V(k)\exp(ikx)$ with the quantum particle also taking on an $\exp(ipx)$ conditional probability (or rather a distribution $\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$) so that $\exp(ikx)\exp(ipx)=\exp(i(p+k)x)$ i.e. an impulse hit based solely on momentum. Mass only enters when one imposes conservation of average energy at each point i.e.

$$1/2m [\text{Sum over } p a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

(This means, however, that mass is present in $a(p)$.)

The above approach seems to apply to nuclear and electromagnetic forces (potential), but a problem arises with the gravitational potential because it does not seem to be impulse based. In other words, $V=GMm/r$ where m is the mass of the quantum particle. Thus:

$$dp = \text{impulse} = \text{Integral } F dt = m \text{ Integral } -GM/r dt \quad ((2))$$

In other words if dt is constant, the impulse depends on m , or said in another manner, the acceleration and not the momentum change of a particle is the same. Quantum mechanics, however, seems to be based on the idea of momentum i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ describes a free particle with momentum p . There is no discernment of mass in $\exp(ipx)$, nor is the wavelength which is proportional to $1/p$. For the nuclear and electromagnetic potentials, one may use an impulse picture with unusual complex probabilities (because the particle momentum is not clearly defined as it changes continually due to impulse hits and there is no time reversal balance). For gravity, one has a contradiction because dp is proportional to m and this is not constant for $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$.

This might suggest treating gravity in a different manner from nuclear or electromagnetic potentials as in the Schrodinger-Newton approach (3). On the other hand, one might treat mass as a constant of the system and still try to treat dp as constant in an impulse situation, as is done in some cases in the literature.

We try to investigate these ideas in more detail in this note.

Statistical Model of Bound Quantum States

In a previous note, we argued that $V(x)$ is really an average which describes an acceleration picture i.e. $dp/dt = mdv/dt = -dV/dx$. We modeled a quantum particle in a bound state based on

impulse hits just as in classical statistical mechanics. An impulse hit comes from $V(x)$ instead of two body collisions in quantum mechanics and so:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V(k,x) \text{ such that } -dV(k,x)/dx = k V(k,x) \text{ b where b is a constant } \quad (3)$$

k is the momentum impulse received by the quantum particle, regardless of which momentum state it is in. In this picture of impulses, we focus entirely on momentum and its conservation. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ both receive the same impulse hit. One does not focus on acceleration.

Unlike classical statistical mechanics where one has time reversal balance i.e. $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and $e_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ yielding a real $f(e_1)$, in a quantum bound state there is no such time reversal. A particle in a state p_1 may be receiving an impulse k_1 to transform into p_1+k_1 , but there is no balanced reaction. As a result, one should not expect a real $P(p/x)$. In fact, if one imposes invariance $V(k,x) = V_k \exp(ikx)$ is a solution and $\exp(ipx)$ is a momentum probability at x of the quantum particle. Thus, wave-like probability emerges, but based solely on momentum i.e. the wavelength is proportional to $1/p$. In other words, one does not distinguish between $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. This seems to apply for electromagnetic and nuclear forces, but not for gravity.

Gravity is extremely weak in quantum bound states using nucleons or electrons, but it seems to be based on "the same acceleration" of particles regardless of their masses and not on the same change in momentum due to an impulse regardless of their masses. Thus, for $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$, both v_1 and v_2 would receive the same acceleration, but dp would be different. This occurs because $V=-GMm/r$ i.e. the potential contains the quantum particle's mass. Thus, one may not establish an impulse picture based on momentum which does not discern mass in the quantum case of a gravitational potential.

One might argue that for a quantum bound problem, mass m is constant for the particle, and simply treat it as a constant in the problem. In other words:

$$V(x) = \sum_k mV(k)\exp(ikx) \quad (4)$$

In such a scenario, one converts a gravitational picture in which one has the same acceleration for different masses into a picture where a given impulse hit of k is given to a quantum object with momentum p . Mass does not come into play in this impulse scenario except for the fact that the probability for the k impulse is $mV(k)\exp(ikx)$ i.e. the probability weight at x is proportional to m . At first, one might argue that this violates the idea of impulse i.e. one might argue that there should be no mass discernment at this point. One may, however, note that mass discernment ultimately enters the quantum problem through ((1)) i.e. conservation of energy with $1/2m$ appearing in the average kinetic energy term. Thus, the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(kpx)$ contains an $a(p)$ which depends specifically on mass while $\exp(ipx)$ depends on momentum i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. Thus, $a(p)$ is a little misleading because $W(x)$ does depend on mass for example, the ground state of an oscillator is $\exp(-.5\sqrt{km}xx)$ so mass is present.

As a result, one might possibly convert a gravitational scenario with constant acceleration for different masses into a picture of identical impulse i.e. momentum changes i.e. different accelerations.

In (2) and other places in the literature, the Schrodinger equation is solved with a GMm/r or mz used as a potential $V(r)$ or $V(z)$. This treats gravity as similar to other forces in that it acts

through constant dp impulses which only on average give the appearance of a constant average regardless of mass. There is, however, a difference in that:

$$V(k,x) = V(k)\exp(ikx)$$

for the nuclear and electromagnetic cases does not contain m explicitly while $V(k,x) = mV(k)\exp(ikx)$ for the gravitational potential does. $\exp(ikx)$ is viewed as giving an impulse hit of k i.e. the same dp for any p state of the quantum particle, but the probability weight $mV(k)\exp(ikx)$ is mass dependent. This possibly alters matters.

An alternative approach for dealing with gravity in the Schrodinger equation is to treat gravity as different from other forces i.e. use the Schrodinger-Newton equation ((2)). In such a case:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x)W(x,t) + m \Phi(x) W^*W = i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) \quad ((5))$$

where $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \Phi(x) = 4 \cdot 3.14 Gm W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$

This allows for the mass density $mW^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ to be created in the usual way with $V(x)$, a non-gravitational potential being a main driver of $W(x,t)$ because gravity is so weak. Thus, an impulse mechanism which cannot discern mass m dominates, but there is a correction due to the classical gravitational self-energy which depends on the quantum $W(x,t)$. One does not convert the gravitational potential into a series of mass dependent impulse hits.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine the role of the gravitational potential in terms of an impulse picture presented in (1) to describe how one converts $V(x)$ into $\sum_k V(k,x)$ where $V(k,x) = V(k)\exp(ikx)$ and an ensemble of momentum states $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ for a quantum bound particle is used. This approach seems to depend entirely on momentum and impulse where the potential piece $V(k,x)$ delivers an impulse k regardless of the mass of the particle. For the gravitational potential there is a problem because the impulse $\int F dt$ contains m if dt is constant. m enters through the form of the force GMm/rr and so $dp = \int F dt$ becomes $dv = \int GM/rr dt$. This means there is a constant acceleration, which is a key of gravity, but for an impulse picture, one wishes to only deal with momentum.

One may try to argue that there is really an impulse picture underlying gravity and that $mV(k)$ is part of the coefficient weight. This is not necessarily a problem as $W(x) = \sum a(p)\exp(ipx)$ contains $a(p)$ which is really mass dependent as well. Ideally, it might have been better not to see mass dependence in the impulse portion of the potential, but given that the average of the impulses yields the overall potential and that the overall potential contains m , it may unavoidable to omit m in the impulse piece.

An alternative is to use the Schrodinger-Newton equation which treats gravity differently from the nuclear or electromagnetic potential. This avoids the unusual nature of forcing a gravitational potential to be based on fixed dp impulse hits.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Base Force (Impulse) Versus Space Based Force ($-dV/dx$) in Classical and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Suda, M. How Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity Can Be Brought Together Journal of Modern Physics Vol 7 No 6 March 2016 **DOI:** [10.4236/jmp.2016.76054](https://doi.org/10.4236/jmp.2016.76054)
https://file.scirp.org/Html/8-7502672_65064.htm
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Schr%C3%B6dinger%E2%80%93Newton_equation